

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

CHANGES IN THE ACTIVITY DYNAMICS OF NADPH SYNTHESIS IN CHICKPEA SEEDLINGS UNDER SALT STRESS CONDITIONS

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Abstract

Cytoplasmic forms of the enzyme Q6PDH, which is the regulator and main enzyme of the pentose phosphate pathway, which is considered one of the ancient ways of glucose breakdown in the tissues of the root system under salt stress conditions and catalyzes the oxidative stage of this pathway, and the cytoplasmic forms of the DMDH enzyme, which is the main enzyme of malate metabolism. It consisted of studying the changes in the dynamics of activity and the indicator of the ratio of their activity.

Keywords: enzyme Q6PDH, pentose phosphate pathway, DMDH enzymes, root system, salt solutions

Recent studies allow us to speculate that both enzymes play an important role in the creation of a defense reaction of plants against the extreme conditions of the surrounding environment and in their adaptation to this environment. Participation of both enzymes in this process is justified by the synthesis of NADPH molecule due to their catalytic effect on their substrates. It is shown that NADPH participates in the neutralization of many biochemical and, in this regard, a number of physiological, including negative effects

of extreme factors.

Table No. 1 below shows the results of experimental studies on the effect of Na-isocationic salt solutions on the activity dynamics of cytoplasmic G6PDH and DMDH enzymes of the root system of pea seedlings and their activity ratio.

If we compare the numbers presented in the table with the similar numbers obtained from the study of the root system of the already considered plant sprouts, it is easy to

Table 1.

On the development of pea seedlings of Na-isocationic salt solutions
Effect on activity dynamics of Q6PDH and DMDH enzymes

Varias	Activite Q6PDH			Activite DMDH			Q6PDH/ DMDH		
	3 day	5 day	7 day	3 day	5 day	7 day	3 day	5 day	7 day
Control	78	99	113	53	59	67	1.47	1.68	1.69
NaCl									
25 mM	93	118	127	61	66	70	1.52	1.79	1.81
50 mM	107	127	137	65	71	75	1.65	1.79	1.83
100 mM	116	121	110	71	76	83	1.63	1.59	1.33
Na ₂ SO ₄									
25 mM	99	131	145	66	69	75	1.50	1.90	1.93
50 mM	113	135	122	70	73	87	1.61	1.85	1.40
100 mM	121	116	101	77	81	96	1.57	1.43	1.05
NaHCO ₃									
25 mM	86	109	112	77	98	109	1.12	1.11	1.03
50 mM	91	110	93	91	86	99	1.00	1.28	0.94
100 mM	103	91	78	99	85	68	1.04	1.07	1.15
Na ₂ CO ₃									
25 mM	89	112	105	81	96	91	1.10	1.17	1.15
50 mM	93	85	89	85	81	75	1.09	1.05	1.19
100 mM	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

it can be seen that Q6PDH and DMDH enzymes occupy an intermediate position between wheat sprouts and bean sprouts according to the level of activity in the tissues of the root system of pea sprouts, which is one of the representatives of other dicotyledonous plants, which is considered more resistant to salt than the bean plant.

As can be seen from the figures presented in the table, the activity of the Q6PDH enzyme gradually increases due to the development of the root system of

pea seedlings in the control variant, and reaches its maximum in the root system of 7-day-old seedlings. During this period, enzyme activity increases by 36.6% compared to 3-day sprouts. Due to the development of the root system, an increase in the activity level of the DMDH enzyme is also observed, although it is weak compared to the Q6PDH enzyme. In this case, compared to 3-day-old seedlings, the corresponding increase in 7-day-old seedlings is 14.8%.

Due to the development of the root system of

sprouts, there are certain changes in the Q6PDH/DMDH indicator. In contrast to the results obtained from the experiments with monocot wheat and barley plants, the value of this indicator in the root system of pea sprouts not only does not decrease, but on the contrary, it slightly increases. If this figure was 1.47 for the root system of 3-day-old sprouts, it gradually increased to 1.69 in the root system of 7-day-old sprouts. In other words, the role of the Q6PDH enzyme in the generation of NADPH potential is not only reduced, but on the contrary, slightly increased due to the development of the root system of pea seedlings.

NaCl salt solutions significantly stimulate the activity of Q6PDH enzyme at relatively low concentrations in the root system of pea seedlings, and at high concentrations, depending on the duration of exposure, they first slow down and then inhibit this process. For example, NaCl salt solutions at concentrations of 25 and 50 mM have a stimulating effect on the activity of the positive Q6PDH enzyme in all incubation periods in a concentration-dependent manner, at a concentration of 100 mM, the stimulating effect continues for 3 days of incubation, this effect weakens in 5-day seedlings, and in 7-day seedlings and is replaced by a weak ginger effect.

NaCl salt solutions have a stimulating effect on DMDH enzyme activity in the root system of pea seedlings during all periods of incubation. However, from the analysis of the Q6PDH/DMDH indicator, it is known that NaCl salt solutions at low concentrations induce more Q6PDH enzyme activity, and more DMDH enzyme activity at higher concentrations. For example, in 7-day-old sprouts, at a concentration of 25 mM, this number is characterized by 1.81, while at a concentration of 100 mM, it decreases to 1.33. A similar picture can be observed in Na₂SO₄ salt solutions. Analogous figures are 1.93 and 1.05 for these salt solutions. That is, in this case, mainly Q6PDH enzyme is induced at low concentration, and DMDH enzyme is induced at high concentration. The obtained results indicate that Q6PDH enzyme is mainly induced under relatively weak stress conditions, and DMDH enzyme under severe stress conditions, as in bean plants. This pattern is also expected in NaHCO₃ and Na₂CO₃ salt solutions. Since the stress created by them is sharper than the stress created by NaCl, Na₂SO₄ salt solutions, in this case the activity of the DMDH enzyme is mainly induced, which is reflected in the Q6PDH/DMDH indicator. Its value is characterized by a value close to unity in both salt solutions.

Thus, the following main conclusions can be drawn from the researches that characterize the root

system of pea seedlings: firstly, the activity level of the Q6PDH enzyme in these tissues is significantly higher than the activity level of the DMDH enzyme, and secondly, the participation of both enzymes in the enrichment of root system cells with NADPH under salt stress conditions however, the role of Q6PDH enzyme mainly increases under relatively weak stress conditions created by Na-isocationic salt solutions, and the role of DMDH enzyme increases under acute stress conditions.

Conclusion: The negative effect of salt solutions on the growth dynamics of seedlings is a multicomponent process. Sprouts, especially their root system, which is primarily in direct contact with salt solutions, are initially affected by the osmotic pressure created by salt solutions, which interferes with the normal performance of water absorption, ion exchange and other vital functions, and such negative effects find their negative effect in the disruption of the normal growth of sprouts. The toxic effect created by salt ions is added to the negative effect caused by the osmotic pressure due to the extension of the incubation period and the accumulation of salt ions inside the cell, which further strengthens the negative effect of the observed salt solutions on the growth dynamics of the seedlings. Therefore, the sharp negative effect of salt solutions on the growth dynamics of sprouts begins to manifest its effect sharply from the 5th day of incubation of sprouts.

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